

User Acceptance and Behaviour Towards Tax Deduction Systems Adoption: An Integrated Technology Acceptance and Usage Model Perspective

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Abstract—The adoption of technology in the tax sector is increasing rapidly. The gaps in the technology infrastructure and information systems have led to a diverse perspective on user behaviour, with users holding various opinions on adopting technology. The study aims to evaluate user behaviour and the user acceptance in the information system called the e-Bupot unification to guide technology development in the tax sector, analyzing six factors: performance expectancy (PE), effort expectancy (EE), social influence (SI), hedonic motivation (HM), Habit (H), Personal Innovativeness (PI) that affect the behavioural intention and use behaviour. The surveys were conducted to 400 responses based in Indonesia area. The result reveals that effort expectancy, social influence, hedonic motivation, habit, and personal innovation have affected the behavioural intention and use behaviour of the technology adoption. The result shows the behavioural intention affects the use behaviour of technology adoption. The performance expectancy was found to have no significant impact on behavioural intention the behavioural intention. The findings show that improving the performance expectancy of its website by the evaluation from the user of this technology is required. By enhancing system usability and providing robust system support for future development to increase the user in the technology adoption. The study adds value to tax policy and technology acceptance literature by evaluating the user behaviour through the UTAUT-3 model showing the user acceptance of this technology adoption for promoting more effective adoption of future digital tax systems in deduction tax.

Keywords—*e-bupot unification, user acceptance, digital transformation, system adoption, UTAUT*

I. INTRODUCTION

Digital transformation has become fundamental reforms in Indonesia. playing a vital role in streamlining tax administration services. By integrating technology into tax collection systems, Indonesia have improved compliance, reduced errors, and lowered the administrative costs [1][2]. Indonesia is investing heavily in infrastructure and various development projects. To support these efforts, substantial funding is needed with tax revenue serving as a crucial source of state income [3]. For maximize tax collection, Indonesia tax system is continuously refined to simplify both processes and infrastructure. Digital tax system functions as an accessible communication tool for the public, aiming to make it easier for the taxpayers to report the tax, make payments, and submit the tax filling that already paid. The approach seeks to boost taxpayer compliance and, in turn, to enhance the government revenue [4][5].

One of the examples of the tax information technology in Indonesia is the e-Bupot unification application. The application is one of the products of the e-Government created by the Directorate General of Taxes (DGT) to help tax corporations withholding tax processing. The e-Bupot unification based on the outlined regulation policy from Directorate General of Taxation PER-24/PJ/2021[6]. The software is accessible through the Directorate General of Taxes official website. It website allows taxpayers to create withholding tax slip and facilitates submission of withholding tax in monthly period[6].

Development of the application e-Bupot Unification make easier for the corporate taxpayer to access because of its webservice application and also it can be accessing for 24 hours everywhere and anytime [7]. The government hopes for this development of application of e-Bupot Unification, that the application will be able to make the level of taxpayer compliance higher, especially on the tax withholder on the achieved its target revenue for the tax sector. The information system development expect to reducing the administrative cost for tax withholder [8].

This study builds on prior research to examine the user experience with e-Bupot unification two years after its implementation. Using the UTAUT-3 framework, the research analyzes key factors influencing the user behaviour and provide the recommendations for improving technology adoption in Indonesia tax sector.

The study is based on several previous studies about the implementation of e-Bupot unification with a different model to test the e-Bupot unification user satisfaction regarding its implementation of system information. The one example of previous study is about the evaluation in implementation of e-Bupot unification. The results of the study show that the variable has a good result towards the user behaviour leading to user acceptance of this application e-Bupot unification, that the user has use the website without any big concern. but because of the research has a limited scope of region, and its research paper has limited time so that its impact some of its variable showing the result not significant. On the study mention that applying other model as suggestion that can help to see the different result of users perspective on the information system[9]. Another previous research study mention that the research have a variable with a insignificant result because of the limited time available for the researcher to collecting the data and the other reason of the limitation of the research paper is the needed of article

UTAUT – 3 model was used because it gives detail the user perspective of technology adoption evaluation [10]. UTAUT 3 model not only provides the framework to understanding the evaluation of the technology adoption from the user behaviour but also incorporates motivational to user to accept and using this technology on their daily basis [11][12].

Data for the research will be analyzed with SmartPLS 4 involving 400 respondents of corporate taxpayers among Indonesia. The 11 hypotheses will be tested to know the evaluation regarding user behaviour on the application leading to the user acceptance of this technology development. The data showed that effort expectancy (EE), social influence (SI), facilitating conditions (FC), hedonic motivation (HM), habit (H), personal innovativeness (PI) affect to behavioural intention (BI) with p-value less than 0.05. For facilitating condition (FC), habit (H), personal innovativeness (PI), and behavioural intention (BI) affect to use behaviour with p-value less than 0.05. The performance expectancy (PE) shows the not significant effect with p-value 0.119.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Performance expectancy

Performance expectancy have a definition related to the degree that individuals believe that using that system will help to increase their task performance [13].

In the context of research about the e-Bupot Unification system, corporate taxpayers perceive that using the system improves their efficiency and accuracy in withholding tax calculations and submissions. Prior research on technology acceptance indicate that when user expect a technology to enhance their performance, their intention to use the technology increase [14][15][16].

The past study found the performance expectancy has affect the user behavioural to tax digitalization adoption from Malaysia show that the performance expectancy of the digitalization tax adoption affect the technology digitilization adoption [15].

H1. Performance expectancy affect user behavioural intention in using e-Bupot Unification.

B. Effort expectancy

Effort expectancy explaining the degree of ease of user with the use of system [14]. When in the case taxpayers perceive that using the e-Bupot unification system convenient and doesn't require much of the effort, they are more likely to intent to use it consistently. Previous studies from the person who make the model show the positive relationship between effort expectancy and behavioural intention in various technological systems [13][16].

H2. Effort expectancy affect user behavioural intention using the e-Bupot Unification.

C. Social Influence

Social influence is the degree to which user perceive that important from the other user (e.g., tax consultant, peers, or authorities) believe they should use the particular system [14]. In the case e-Bupot Unification, social factor such as opinion from colleagues, peers, and the regulatory environment can influence a taxpayers intention adopt the system. From the previous study social influence has affect the social influence

is the one of the factors that effect of the use of the tax digitalization in Malaysia [15].

H3. Social influence affect user behavioural intention in using e-Bupot Unification.

D. Facilitating Conditions

Facilitating conditions related to the perceived of availability of tools and the support of using of the systems for the user [14]. Within the tax deduction system, taxpayers who feel they have sufficient resources, such as support, training, or IT infrastructure, are more inclined to intend to use and ultimately adopt the system.

From the previous research about the UTAUT-3 model on technology adoption show that for facilitating conditions and behavioural intention show insignificant effect other than the facilitating condition and use behaviour have the affect each other. So when the facilitating conditions have reaching to positive they will use the technology directly [10][16]. The facilitating condition impacts the use of the tax digitalization in Malaysia the one of impact the user acceptance in tax digitalization in Malaysia is the facilitating conditions that provide by the government [15].

H4a. Facilitating conditions affect user behavioural intentions in using e-Bupot unification.

H4b. Facilitating condition affect use behaviour in using e-Bupot unification

E. Hedonic Motivation

Hedonic motivation refers to the fun or pleasure derived from using a technology, which has been shown to influence technology adoption and usage [14]. In the context of research about e-Bupot Unification, the corporate taxpayers find the system enjoyable and rewarding to use, they are more likely to adopt it.

The previous study shows that the significant effect from between the hedonic motivation with the user behavioural intention [17][18].

H5. Hedonic motivation affects user behavioural intention in using e-Bupot unification.

F. Habit

Habit reflects the extent to which individuals tend to perform behaviours automatically due to learning [14]. If the taxpayers develop habit of using the e-Bupot system, the habit can positively influence both intentions to continue using the system and their actual usage behaviour.

The previous study shows that the significant result between the habit of the user within the behavioural intention and the use behaviour in its application [10].

H6a. Habit affect user behavioural intention in using e-Bupot unification.

H6b. Habit affect use behaviour in using e-Bupot unification.

G. Personal Innovativeness

Personal innovativeness refers to an individual willingness and tendency to adopt the new technologies [19]. In the context of information systems, individual with high personal innovativeness is often more inclined to explore and experiment with the new technologies. The trait makes them more open to adopting the innovations such as the system called e-Bupot Unification. According to the studies, personal

innovativeness has shown to positively affect behaviour on previous study show that the relationship between personal innovativeness and behavioural intention show that positive effect [10]. People who are more innovative are more likely to perceive new technology as beneficial and easier to use, which turn increases in their intention to use it.

Individual are more innovative tend to be early adopters and are likely to engage in the use of technologies [20]. In the context of e-Bupot unification, users with high personal innovativeness will likely explore the system more frequently and confidently and use it without no hesitation.

Several studies in technology adoption have shown that personal innovativeness can lead to a higher actual use of technologies and the intention to use the technology [21] [22].

H7a. Personal innovativeness affect user behavioural intention in using of e-Bupot unification.

H7b. Personal innovativeness affect use behaviour in using e-Bupot unification

H. Behavioural Intention

Behavioural intention is the strongest predictor of actual use behaviour according to the UTAUT – 1 model [13]. In the case research of e-Bupot Unification user behaviour, user with the strong intention for using the system are more likely to use the accept this system and use it directly

In previous study on technology adoption using UTAUT model, it was found that behavioural intention significantly influences that actual use of application [10][16].

H8. Behavioural intention affects use behaviour in using e-Bupot unification.

III. METHODOLOGY

Fig. 1. Research model.

The UTAUT -3 model presented in Fig. 1 was chosen for its ability to provide the framework to understand the evaluation of the technology adoption from the user behaviour and motivational to user to accept its technology on their daily basis.

The survey involved 400 respondents distributed across Indonesia. The sample was evenly distributed to capture varying perspective on tax deduction technology adoption in Indonesia. The Slovin formula was applied to determine a sample size with margin of error of 0.05, Indonesian population of corporate taxpayers is 12,4 million, using the

calculation the authors able determine a sample size of 400 respondents [23]. Table I contains the details of the respondent gathered. The raw data for the study has been made to the public.

TABLE I. RESPONDENT DATA.

Aspect	Data
1. Age	
• 18-24	48 (12%)
• 25-34	150 (37.5%)
• 35-44	118 (29.5%)
• 45-54	47 (11.7%)
• 55-64	37 (9.3%)
• >65	0
2. Gender	
• Male	262 (65.5%)
• Female	138 (34.5%)
3. Educational degree	
• Highschool	1 (0.3%)
• Diploma	50 (12.5%)
• Bachelor	255 (63.7%)
• Magister	80 (20%)
• Doctoral	14 (3.5%)
4. Job	
• Employee	112 (28%)
• Entrepreneur	80 (20%)
• Freelancer	202 (50.5%)
• Government Employee	6 (1.5%)
5. Taxpayer Category	
• Individual Taxpayers	62 (15.5%)
• Corporate Taxpayers	338 (84.5%)
6. Have you ever used e-Bupot Unifaction	
• Yes	390 (97.5%)
• No	10 (2.5%)
7. How long have you been used	
• Not using the app	10 (2.5%)
• <6 month	3 (0.7%)
• 6 month – 1 year	267 (66.8%)
• 1-2 years	120 (30%)
• > 2 years	0

The study using the convenient sampling technique for the timely efficiency and other practical reason. As the corporate taxpayers is widely and everywhere for the practical reason the user of e-Bupot unification asked to fill by google form based on the five-point Likert scale and distributed through social media platforms such as WhatsApp, Facebook, Instagram, and Line to reach the user of the technology adoption. The primary data was conducted during the month of September 2024 – Oktober 2024.

The research data will be analyses using the Partial Least Square (PLS) – SEM method once the data is collected, based on the hypotheses outlined above. SmartPLS 4.0 will employed to generate the analytical result. The analysis will include testing the outer model, inner model, and conducting hypothesis testing to evaluate the result of each variable hypotheses [24].

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Fig. 2 show the calculation result with smart PLS 4.0. The details of each explanation in the calculation result will be explained below.

A. Indicator and Construct Validity

Table II contains information on the outer loading. Which shows each of the indicators and the constructs. A value of outer loading more than 0.708 is normally preferred [25]. The test that was done using smartPLS shows that every indicator

of every variable has load factor of greater than 0.7 hence supporting the measurement value.

Fig. 2. Calculation results.

TABLE II. OUTER LOADING

Factors	Indicator	Outer Loadings	Validity
Performance Expectancy (PE)	PE1	0.864	Valid
	PE2	0.865	Valid
	PE3	0.857	Valid
	PE4	0.866	Valid
Effort Expectancy (EE)	EE1	0.870	Valid
	EE2	0.874	Valid
	EE3	0.866	Valid
	EE4	0.874	Valid
Social Influence (SI)	SI1	0.864	Valid
	SI2	0.888	Valid
	SI3	0.872	Valid
Facilitating Conditions (FC)	FC1	0.874	Valid
	FC2	0.871	Valid
	FC3	0.850	Valid
	FC4	0.868	Valid
Hedonic Motivation (HM)	HM1	0.856	Valid
	HM2	0.874	Valid
	HM3	0.857	Valid
	HM4	0.886	Valid
Habit (H)	H1	0.879	Valid
	H2	0.879	Valid
	H3	0.864	Valid
Personal Innovativeness (PI)	PI1	0.874	Valid
	PI2	0.876	Valid
	PI3	0.877	Valid
	PI4	0.865	Valid
Behavioural Intention (BI)	BI1	0.877	Valid
	BI2	0.880	Valid
	BI3	0.872	Valid
	BI4	0.874	Valid
Use Behaviour (UB)	UB1	0.883	Valid
	UB2	0.880	Valid
	UB3	0.890	Valid

B. Reliability

Table III below shows the AVE and Cronbach's alpha. The AVE is again employed to verify validity of the data with the purpose of checking that convergent validity condition. AVE should be a good number and has a threshold of 0.5 [25]. As depicted in Table III, the AVE test shows that each construct has more than the recommended 0.5 square value for the AVE test.

TABLE III. CONSTRUCT RELIABILITY AND VALIDITY

Factor	AVE	Cronbach' Alpha	Reliability
Performance Expectancy	0.745	0.866	Reliable
Effort Expectancy	0.759	0.894	Reliable
Social Influence	0.765	0.847	Reliable
Facilitating Conditions	0.750	0.889	Reliable
Hedonic Motivation	0.760	0.895	Reliable
Habit	0.764	0.845	Reliable
Personal Innovativeness	0.763	0.896	Reliable
Behavioural Intention	0.767	0.899	Reliable
Use Behaviour	0.782	0.861	Reliable

Cronbach's Alpha is used to justify the reliability of a variable with range of 0.6 and 0.95 for being reliable[25]. According to the internal consistency reliability test presented Table III above, all the variables have coefficients of 0.6 and above 0.95 as the highest.

C. Path Coefficient

The table below shows the result of the path coefficients, including the p-values used to evaluate the hypotheses in the study. A hypothesis is considered significant if the p-value is equal to or less than 0.005 [25]. Table IV indicated that all the hypotheses are significant, except for performance expectancy with a p-value of 0.119.

TABLE IV. PATH MODEL ASSESSMENT

Path Model	Original Sample	P-value	Significance
PE → BI	0.072	0.119	Not Significant
EE → BI	0.143	0.007	Significant
SI → BI	0.155	0.005	Significant
FC → BI	0.191	0.006	Significant
FC → UB	0.193	0.018	Significant
HM → BI	0.149	0.002	Significant
H → BI	0.136	0.004	Significant
H → UB	0.217	0.003	Significant
PI → BI	0.124	0.005	Significant
PI → UB	0.203	0.002	Significant
BI → UB	0.155	0.005	Significant

TABLE V. R SQUARE

Factor	R ²
Behavioural Intention	0.644
Use Behaviour	0.564

An R² value of 0.644 for Behavioral Intention (BI) indicates that 64% of the variation in the variable is explained the independent variables, while the remaining 36% is attributed to other unknown factors. Otherwise, an R² value of 0.564 for Use Behaviour (UB) suggests that 56% of the changes in the variable can be accounted for by the independent variables, leaving 44% due to unknown influences [25].

D. Discussion

1) *Performance expectancy affect behavioural intention in using e-Bupot unification:* Performance expectancy affects behavioural intention, Table IV shows that unaccepted with p-value 0.119. Previous study related to the model shows the insignificant impact towards performance expectancy and behavioural intention [26]. The is caused by the user time inefficiency and the performance of the information system not meet the user requirement based on the user behaviour of using the application. Its relate to the traffic and error of the

system because a lot of people especially in their withholding tax process using it, so the performance of its webservice still have a lack of problem, so due to the lack of the webservice its need to be improve to make the user more acceptable related to this technology development [27].

2) *Effort expectancy affect user behavioural intention in using e-Bupot unification:* From the user behaviour evaluation that based on the users finding the website is enjoy accessing because it accessible leading to the user acceptance through this technology. The result show the similar previous study about e-Bupot unification but with a different model for checking the technology adoption the perceive ease of use have a positive effect [7].

3) *Social influence affect user behavioural intention in using e-Bupot unification:* Social influence is the one who can impact the use of technology. The social influence shows that it's significant to the user's intention to use information technology. Based on the previous study apply the model shows that the social influence have a positive effect the technology adoption [26][28][15]. The result shows that the behavioural intention of the user of e-Bupot unification from the user social environment, the social that affect the behavioural intention led to user acceptance and use the system on their daily basis.

4) *Facilitating conditions affect user behavioural intention and use behaviour in using e-Bupot unification:* Table V shows that the facilitating conditions affect both behavioural intention and use of behaviour. From the evaluation from the user show that if the user want to know about the e-Bupot unification there's so many tutorial of this apps in media platform even in its own website in DJP online [29]. Based on the previous research that the its positive effect only on the behavioural intention not the use behaviour[10][15]. But in the case the significant effect is shown in both behavioural intention and use behaviour based on the evaluation of the user lead to the successful of the user accept the system.

5) *Hedonic motivation affect user behavioural intention in using e-Bupot unification:* Hedonic motivation has shown significant way in both behavioural intentions. Based on the behaviour of users of this system, it shows that the user motivation that e-Bupot unification helps their report withholding tax process more enjoyable and feel motivated when doing the reporting deduction process. The reason for evaluation of the user led to the user acceptance of this e-Bupot unification based on the effect on the user intention to use this webservice. Previous study show that the personal innovativeness have a significant relationship to behavioural intention [28].

6) *Habit affect user behavioural intention and use behaviour in using e-Bupot unification:* Habits affect both behavioural intention and use of behaviour so when the user used this system in their daily basis or becoming a habit. This happens because the user behaviour evaluation led to the user getting used to the system that led to the acceptance of this system because this system already implemented for two years lead to the acceptance of this system to support the reporting of deduction system based on the evaluation from

the user of this e-Bupot unification. The previous study using the UTAUT-3 model shows the significant way [10].

7) *Personal innovativeness affect user behavioural intention and use behaviour in using e-Bupot unification:* Personal innovationess shows the significant for both behavioural intention and use behaviour with p-value of 0.005 and 0.002 so the hypothesis accepted. Based on the user behaviour evaluation from the questionnaire users are open to adopting this technology freely and due to this personal innovationess, the user accepts the information system e-Bupot unification and actively seeks the newest information of the technology. The user Previous study of the model shows the significant effect to the variable between the personal innovativeness effect the behavioural intention and use behaviour [26][10].

8) *Behavioural intention affect use behaviour in use behaviour in e-Bupot unification:* The significant effect of behavioural intention towards behavioural intention shows a significant result and this plays an important role among the variables in this research because when the user's behaviour from answering the questionnaire shows the intention to use this system it led to the use behaviour and leading to the acceptance of this technology make user use this system for such a long period. It shows that the p-value is 0,001. The previous study about UTAUT-3 model show the significant relationship between the behavioural intention toward behavioural intention [10][15][30].

V. CONCLUSION

The study introduces a new perspective by incorporating personal innovativeness as an additional key of variable in assessing technology acceptance within a business setting. It also offers valuable insights into the tax sector on essential factors that could improve the future adoption of the tax sector technology. The study serves as an input from user for government in developing technology adoption in the tax sector. The research also serves as a guide for other researchers when conducting similar studies, both in the field of taxation and other areas of technology adoption. This study concludes that from the user behaviour through this development technology, causing the user acceptance especially from the corporate taxpayer using this technology on their daily basis.

The study contributes to the technology adoption literature in taxation field by applying the UTAUT – 3 model to e-Bupot unification users. Factors such as social influence and facilitating conditions are key determinants of technology adoption. Performance expectancy from the website through the user doesn't make it the requirement due to the traffic of its website when the user must access it so that it does not meet the user satisfaction towards the tax deduction system.

The limitation of time is the main concern in the study lead to limited area and limited respondent. Also, the limitation of the literature regarding this topic is concerning for the author to find the references for the study.

For further research should involve a broader regional sample to capture more diverse perspectives on the user acceptance and behaviour on the tax withholding information system implementation. Qualitative methods are also conducted in the research to give deeper insight from the taxpayer directly. Additional factors can be added in the next

study like trust using the system to expand understanding of the user acceptance and behaviour on the tax deduction system adoption. The research needs more literature lead to making more of the paper with different model to test the user acceptance and user behaviour on the technology adoption tax in Indonesia.

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